

USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING LISTENING TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation: This article examines how innovative technologies enhance listening instruction for young learners. It highlights tools like interactive apps, AR storytelling, digital storybooks, gamified activities, and podcasts, which make lessons engaging and effective.

Key words: listening skills, young learners, language acquisition, technology in education, digital tools, interactive learning, Gamified listening activities.

Listening is one of the foundational skills in language acquisition, particularly for young learners, as it lays the groundwork for developing other language skills such as speaking, reading, and writing. In an increasingly digital world, innovative pedagogical technologies are transforming the way educators teach listening, making lessons more engaging, interactive, and effective. This article explores the importance of listening, the role of technology in enhancing listening instruction, and practical ways to integrate these tools into the classroom to support young learners.

Listening is the first language skill children develop, often before they speak or understand the structure of a language. It plays a crucial role in building vocabulary, understanding sentence patterns, and developing communicative competence. For young learners, listening is not only essential for language development but also for cognitive and emotional growth.

Through listening, children can absorb new vocabulary and phrases in context, develop an ear for pronunciation, rhythm, and intonation, improve comprehension skills by processing information and making sense of it, build confidence to participate in conversations and other language activities.

Given the importance of listening, teachers must ensure that their lessons are engaging, meaningful, and suited to the developmental stages of young learners. Innovative pedagogical technologies can play a transformative role in achieving these goals.

The integration of technology in education has revolutionized how students learn and interact with information. When applied to listening

instruction, it opens new possibilities for creating immersive and interactive experiences that cater to the needs of young learners. The following are some of the most impactful technological tools and approaches for teaching listening:

1. Interactive Audio-Based Applications

Applications like Lingokids, Fun English, and ABC mouse incorporate listening activities into games and lessons. These apps use storytelling, music, and games to engage young learners while exposing them to spoken language in diverse contexts. Children can listen to a story, answer comprehension questions, and practice vocabulary through interactive tasks.

2. Augmented Reality (AR) Storytelling

AR tools such as Wonderscope and Narrator AR bring listening materials to life by combining audio narration with animated visual elements. This immersive storytelling experience helps children visualize and better understand what they hear, improving their comprehension and retention of the material.

3. Gamified Listening Activities

Gamification tools like Kahoot!, Quizizz, and Classcraft incorporate audio-based challenges into their activities. For example, children may listen to a set of instructions or sounds and then complete tasks such as matching, identifying, or sequencing. These games make listening fun while encouraging active participation and attention to detail.

To maximize the effectiveness of technology in teaching listening, it is essential to design activities that are structured, purposeful, and engaging. Below are strategies for successfully integrating technology into listening lessons:

1. Pre-Listening Activities

Before using technological tools, set the stage with pre-listening activities:

- Introduce key vocabulary and phrases.
- Discuss the theme or context of the listening material.
- Use visual aids or prompts to activate prior knowledge and generate interest.

2. Interactive Listening Tasks

During the listening activity, encourage active engagement:

- Use apps or games that require children to listen carefully and respond.
- Ask comprehension questions to check understanding.
- Include tasks like matching sounds to images, sequencing events, or identifying key details.

3. Post-Listening Activities

After the listening task, reinforce learning through follow-up activities:

- Have students retell the story or summarize what they heard.
- Create art, songs, or role-plays based on the listening material.
- Use quizzes or games to review key points.

Innovative pedagogical technologies have revolutionized the way listening is taught to young learners. By incorporating interactive apps, AR storytelling, digital audiobooks, gamified activities, and other tools, teachers can create dynamic and engaging listening lessons that cater to the needs and interests of their students. When thoughtfully integrated, these technologies not only enhance listening skills but also foster a love for language learning that can last a lifetime. Educators should embrace these innovations while maintaining a balanced approach to ensure the holistic development of their learners..

List of used literature:

1. Brown, H. D. (2007). Teaching by Principles: An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. Pearson Education.
2. Richards, J. C., & Rodgers, T. S. (2014). Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching. Cambridge University Press.
3. Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A Framework for Teacher Knowledge. Teachers College Record, 108(6), 1017–1054.
4. Moydinova, S. I., & Abdurahmanova, I. (2023). METHODS OF WORKING WITH LEXICAL MATERIAL AT THE INITIAL STAGE OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 73-76.
5. Moydinova, S. I., & Khakimova, K. (2023). USING INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION FOR PRE-SCHOOL LEARNERS. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 61-64.
6. Moydinova, S. I., & Bazarova, G. (2023). USING SONGS IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 2(3), 65-68.
7. Moydinova, S. I., & Abdumuminova, S. (2023). TYPES OF TEXTS BY SPECIALTY AND THEIR USAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES. "TRENDS OF MODERN SCIENCE AND PRACTICE", 1(1), 72-75.
8. Moydinova, S. (2022). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF NON-COMMUNICATIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE METHODS. Thematics Journal of Education, 7(1).

9. Moydinova, S. (2024). SOME COMMENTS ON THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TEACHING READING AT NON-PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY. *Молодые ученые*, 2(4), 98-100.
10. Moydinova, S., & Ne'matova, M. (2024, February). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA CHET TILI O'QITISHDA O'YINLARNING AXAMIYATI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 43-46).
11. Moydinova, S. (2024). O'QISHNING KASBIY MAHORATNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDAGI ROLI VA O'QISH TURLARINING TASNIFI. Interpretation and researches.
12. Moydinova, S. (2024). NOFILOLOGIK OLIYGOHLARDA KASBIY MATNLARNI TANLASH MEZONLARI VA O'QIB TUSHUNISHGA O'RGATISH TAMOYILLARI. *Инновационные исследования в современном мире: теория и практика*, 3(5), 107-109.
13. Moydinova, S. (2024). SOME COMMENTS ON THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC FEATURES OF TEACHING READING AT NON-PHILOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY. *Молодые ученые*, 2(4), 98-100.
14. Moydinova, S., & Ne'matova, M. (2024, February). MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA CHET TILI O'QITISHDA O'YINLARNING AXAMIYATI. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS*. (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 43-46).
15. Moydinova, S. (2023). NOFILOLOGIK OLIYGOHLARDA CHET TIL O'QITISHDA MATN TANLASH MEZONLARI. *Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi*, (10), 347-351.